

What are High School Students' Mental Representations about Relativity Theory?

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Considering the significance of approaches related to Modern Physics in basic education, this research explores the outcomes following the implementation of activities with high school students that incorporate both Special and General Relativity Theory. Given the inherently abstract nature of this theory, fostering the development of mental representations among students becomes a valuable tool for enhancing comprehension. Consequently, an analysis was conducted through video recordings of students with the goal of identifying the mental representations employed in the comprehension of Relativity. The findings revealed evidence of the use of both verbal (propositional) and nonverbal (imagistic) mental representations in various situations. These results align with the Dual Coding Theory, as students employed both coding systems in their learning process.

Keywords: Mental Representations; Relativity; Dual Coding.

Introduction

The fundamental goal of basic education is to prepare students with the ability to comprehend the contemporary world and foster civic awareness. In this context, Modern and Contemporary Physics (MCP) plays an increasingly pivotal role in elucidating the developments of the 20th and 21st centuries, explaining emerging technologies (Boublil et al., 2023).

Einstein's Relativity Theory (RT) holds particular appeal for students in this domain (Hartle, 2006; Henriksen et al., 2014; Kersting, 2019). The advancement of RT has not only contributed to the development of widely utilized technologies, such as the Global Positioning System (GPS), but has also gained visibility through recent detections of gravitational waves and images of black holes, drawing attention on social media and bringing the theory closer to the reality of students.

However, the approach to RT remains uncommon in Brazilian and global classrooms, as noted by Kaur et al. (2017); Pitts et al. (2013). A prevalent obstacle to the integration of RT into educational curricula is the inherent complexity of the subject, posing challenges for students in grasping its intricacies. Teachers and students encounter various difficulties related to RT, with a primary concern revolving around the capacity to abstractly visualise relativistic situations (Ruggiero et al., 2021; Steier & Kersting, 2019; Yavaş & Kızılcık, 2016).

Given this educational landscape, an advantageous strategy for enhancing the learning process of RT could be the construction of mental representations by students, facilitating a deeper understanding of the theory and the associated phenomena.

Dual Coding Theory (DCT)

Einstein's Relativity Theory (RT) stands out for challenging various aspects of common sense, introducing novel notions of space and time that diverge from students' familiar experiences in their daily lives (Kraus, 2008). Consequently, the construction of mental representations may

prove beneficial in enhancing students' grasp of the theory.

Mental representations are internal constructs individuals devise to capture their experiences. Human cognition, involving both nonverbal objects and language, operates through the simultaneous utilization of two coding systems: verbal, employing language, and nonverbal, utilizing imagery (Clark & Paivio, 1991).

The structural representations of dual coding theory refer to relatively stable long-term memory information corresponding to perceptually identifiable objects and activities, both verbal and nonverbal (Paivio, 1986, p. 54).

These two autonomous systems are structurally and functionally distinct, enabling individual or combined activation. One system processes information and generates nonverbal representations, creating mental imagery, while the other system manages language and propositions. A proposition is defined as “an abstract subject-predicate statement that can be evaluated for its truth value within the bounds of a logical theoretical system” (Paivio, 1986, p. 9).

According to the DCT, mental representations originate from the internalization of external perceptual experiences and are stored in modality-specific representational structures as symbolic coding systems: the verbal one, represented by *logogens*, and the nonverbal one, represented by *imagens*. In verbal structures, smaller units progressively organize into larger ones. Conversely, nonverbal units are available simultaneously, facilitating parallel information processing.

Furthermore, “related context effects influence not only the relative activation of verbal and nonverbal systems but also the patterns of activation of verbal and nonverbal systems” (Clark & Paivio, 1991, p. 156). Therefore, the origin and nature of external stimuli can impact the likelihood of which type of mental representation is employed. The activation of nonverbal representations correlates with the concreteness of stimuli and is linked to sensory experiences, meaning that words associated with concrete and sensory experiences tend to evoke mental imagery. Conversely, more abstract concepts, not easily linked to sensory experiences, tend to generate verbal representations, potentially in the form of propositions.

Then, both systems are important for an individual's cognition:

Performance is mediated by the joint activity of verbal and nonverbal systems, with the relative contribution of each system depending on characteristics of the task and cognitive abilities and habits of the performer (Paivio, 1986, p. 201).

In summary, for a comprehensive understanding of a phenomenon, individuals use both information coding systems. Consequently, in our analysis, we aimed to identify the presence of mental representations – verbal (logically formed sentences) and nonverbal (imagery or mental simulations) – in students' cognitive structures following their participation in the activities.

Research Question

Given the aforementioned context, this research endeavours to identify whether and which mental representations are constructed and employed by high school students in the learning process of both Special and General Relativity Theory. Stemming from the research problem, “*What kind of mental representations do students use to process relativistic phenomena?*”, we aimed to explore the coding systems utilized by students in grappling with relativistic phenomena related to both time and space.

Methodology

This research comprised two phases: initially, an exploration focused solely on Special Relativity (SR), followed by a subsequent phase incorporating General Relativity (GR). In both segments, high school senior students actively participated in the data collection, engaging with various instructional resources, including videos, animated gifs, mock-ups, discussions, and computer simulations. The activities encompassed diverse forms of representation to elucidate phenomena related to time and space, incorporating both verbal and nonverbal stimuli for the comprehensive study of all phenomena.

The first phase of the study took place during physics curricular classes in the second half of 2019. Students underwent pre-test and post-test questionnaires, leading to the selection of 14 students for individual interviews conducted by the teacher-researcher. The interviews followed the Report Aloud protocol (Trevisan et al., 2019), fostering a continuous dialogue between the interviewer and interviewee. During these interviews, students articulated their thoughts while recounting their experiences with the activities.

The second phase of the research involved eight students in an extracurricular short course during the second half of 2022. Throughout the course, students collaborated in small groups to perform various activities, stimulating discussions among them. The analysis of these activities included the examination of worksheets submitted by students, complemented by video recordings capturing their interactions. Utilizing this data, the students' dialogues were scrutinized to discern their reasoning processes.

Both the interviews in the first part and the recorded activities in the second part were fully transcribed. The transcripts underwent textual analysis to identify the verbal representations used by the students, taking the form of logically connected verbal sentences. This analysis drew upon characteristics of verbal representations and their usage as presented by Clark and Paivio (1991). Indicators of the presence of verbal representations included the use of extensive language to describe a situation, incorporation of verbal details, or auditory processing, suggesting the student was 'hearing' the information in their mind.

Verbal representations could manifest as complete sentences or even as single words, depending on the complexity of the situation. Additionally, "verbal representations are generally processed in a serial or sequential manner" (Clark & Paivio, 1991, p. 151). Hence, when employing verbal representations, students sequentially provide a verbal description of a situation, presenting a logical sequence of interconnected events.

The Depictive Gestural Analysis (Monaghan & Clement, 1999; Stephens & Clement, 2010) was also employed to explore the connection between descriptive gestures performed by students and their mental images, i.e., nonverbal representations. This analysis assumes a correlation between the depictive gestures executed by students and the mental imagery processes in their cognition.

In an effort to identify these depictive gestures, indicators such as students' hand movements during dialogue were used. Consequently, gestures serve as a means for students to externalize their thoughts, indicating their mental imagery or nonverbal representations. Depictive gestures can be seen as a parallel 'speech' that occurs alongside verbal communication. When jointly analysed, it becomes possible to discern the mental representations employed during the activities.

Results and Discussion

Through the analysis of results, it was possible to identify the use of both types of mental

representations, verbal and nonverbal, by students for both SR and GR. The results presented below show evidence of these mental representations first for SR and, afterwards, for GR.

Special Relativity

Among the students who participated in the first part of the research, student A18 exhibited evidence of the use of nonverbal representations when grappling with the space contraction phenomenon. In addressing questions 1 and 3 of the tests, which pertained to the measured distance between two trucks in situations of varying relative velocities, A18 demonstrated an understanding of the relationship of this phenomenon with the speed of the reference frame.

A18: . . . That the speed is high, so the higher the speed, the shorter the distance will be.

E: . . . And do you imagine that?

A18: Yes, I imagine [# NAV4 20:09] the path literally decreasing you know, as if it were in the GIF [used in the slides' presentation], but then the path and not the spaceship, right.

This student manifested a distinct mental image, specifically, a nonverbal representation constructed to comprehend the space contraction phenomenon. A18 described this representation as a spaceship decreasing in length as it moves. The ship, as conveyed by A18, along with his depictive gestures (Monaghan & Clement, 1999), bore a striking resemblance to an animated GIF used in slides, suggesting the existence of a mental simulation for this relativistic situation.

Figure 1. Gesture #NAV4 performed by A18 (left) where he places both hands in front of himself and moves the left hand close to the right hand, indicating the change in the spaceship length; and GIF from the slides (right).

Therefore, A18 translated the previously observed situation in class to the questions of the post-test (“the faster the truck was, the shorter its path would be”), providing correct responses. Even though multiple representations were used during the classes to approach the space contraction, A18 primarily relied on the visual representation presented through the GIF to construct his personal mental representation of the phenomenon.

This student could construct a nonverbal representation, employing a mental simulation accessible to him offline to solve a distinct problem. In accordance with the DCT, concrete concepts like space, tied to sensory experiences, are more likely to evoke the use of the nonverbal system and, consequently, nonverbal representations.

Another participant from the first part of the research, student A14, similarly exhibited indications of using mental representations. A14 demonstrated an understanding of time dilation and employed verbal representations when elucidating her responses to questions 5 and 7 of the tests, which pertained to the time interval of a ship trip for two friends in situations with varying relative velocities.

A14: I think it would be very bigger, like, more than one year of difference . . . from each other. . . I think about the little rocket, about the brother [*twins' paradox*], because the brother who had traveled was younger than the brother who has stayed on Earth.

It is possible to note that this student did not use images but relied on propositions to address time dilation. According to A14, she recalled a situation discussed during the activities, indicating the use of verbal representations. Additionally, A14 did not perform any depictive gestures nor allude to imagining anything directly, signifying the absence of mental images and nonverbal representations.

When questioned about what student recalled while answering the question, A14 answered 'about the brothers, because the brother that had gone traveling was younger than the brother that had stayed on Earth'. This suggests that the student verbalized the example and constructed a mental representation of the concept without relying on visual aids or simulations.

In the post-test, A14 accurately predicted the answers to questions concerning time dilation and articulated logical arguments during the interview, employing verbal reasoning to resolve the problem. The presence of a sequential and organized verbal structure suggests the existence of a verbal mental representation (Clark & Paivio, 1991) of time dilation – where less time passes for a moving reference – indicating a sound understanding of the concept.

According to the DCT, this outcome aligns with expectations. Abstract concepts, such as time, which are not closely tied to sensory experiences, are likely to prompt the use of the verbal system and verbal representations.

General Relativity

Regarding the GR, the results obtained by the second part of the research mirrored those of the first. When addressing proposed question about spacetime distortion caused by the massive star Sirius, a group of three students discussed about the light bend around it. Evidence of the use of nonverbal representations by these students was identified as they engaged in collaborative depictive gestures during the discussion.

P3: Yes, we saw this in another class, do you remember that she [*teacher*] explained that depending on the angle that you look, you can't see [#LUZ1 01:54] the light.

P6: Yes, if I'm not wrong, you were seeing here [#LUZ2 01:58], and the light was here.

P3: And then, it made a curve [#LUZ3 02:02].

In this activity, P3 and P6 were elucidating the concept of light bend to a third student, P10, who faced challenges in imagining the situation (Steier & Kersting, 2019). Throughout the dialogue, it became apparent that the students attempted to visualize the situation, employing collaborative depictive gestures to articulate their mental images, namely, their nonverbal mental representations. Moreover, the students referenced the classes where an animated GIF was used to illustrate this particular situation.

Figure 2. (1) Gesture #LUZ1 performed by P3 pointing indicating the massive object, and with her hand indicating where an observer sees a light beam passing by it; (2) Gesture #LUZ2 performed by P16, interacting with P3 gesture, where he points where the light is emitted and where it would be observed; (3) Gesture #LUZ3 performed by P3 where she indicates the light beam trajectory.

Despite the variety of representations employed to approach the light bending during the classes, the students primarily relied on the visual resource provided by the animated GIF to understand and explain the proposed situation. As the students described during the activity, and as suggested by their depictive gestures (Monaghan & Clement, 1999), they constructed a nonverbal mental representation dealing with the light bending phenomenon. Both P3 and P16 used their gestures to describe their imaginative processes and establish a communication with P10.

The situation resented in the exercise that the students were solving, encompasses highly imagistic concepts, fostering the use of nonverbal representations (Clark & Paivio, 1991). Additionally, it is crucial to emphasize the collaborative process of imagination established by them (Steier & Kersting, 2019). Through this communication, the students were able to reach a collective conclusion regarding the solution of the problem.

In responding to another question, which dealt with gravitational time dilation, student P9 exhibited some evidence of the use of verbal mental representations. The question involved a scene from the movie 'Interstellar', which had been discussed in the classes, and inquired about the difference in the time intervals between those who approached the black hole and those who remained on the spaceship.

While answering this question, no depictive gestures were identified during the students' dialogue. Furthermore, although students were encouraged to draw or visually present their answers using diagrams, P9 opted to provide her answer solely through text, describing the phenomenon that occurred.

In student's response, she explained that "the time interval near a massive object is smaller than the time interval for an observer far away". Notably, in P9's answer, she established a connection between the passage of time and the distance from a massive body. The interlinked sentences reflect a logical relationship among them.

Figure 3. P9's answer to the question about gravitational time dilation.

Tal fato se dá devido a dilatação temporal gravitacional, que diz que o intervalo de tempo próximo ao objeto massivo é menor do que o intervalo de tempo para um observador muito distante. Nesse caso, para Amélia e Cooper, que estavam próximos de um buraco negro, o tempo passou muito mais devagar do que para quem ficou na Terra.

Hence, these indications suggest that this student constructed and employed verbal mental representations to address gravitational time dilation and comprehend it. This outcome aligns with expectations, given that time dilation involves abstract concepts (such as time) not directly linked to sensory experiences. According to DCT, such concepts tend to favor the use of the verbal coding system (Paivio, 1986).

Conclusion

In this work, we emphasize the importance of incorporating Relativity Theory into school curricula. Given its complexity and the scarcity of observable consequences in everyday life, students often encounter significant difficulty in imagine relativistic phenomena (Ruggiero et al., 2021; Steier & Kersting, 2019). Therefore, we posited the hypothesis that the development of mental representations by students could enhance their comprehension of Relativity Theory. This study aims to identify the types of mental representations that emerge in students' learning processes.

The analysis of the results revealed the usage of both verbal (propositional) and non-verbal (imagistic) mental representations by students when dealing with SR and GR. It was also possible to note that verbal mental representations allowed the students to interpret more abstract phenomena involving time dilation for both Special and General Relativity. As time is an abstract concept not directly linked to sensory experiences, this outcome aligns with the Dual Coding Theory (Clark & Paivio, 1991; Paivio, 1986).

Conversely, nonverbal representations were associated with more concrete situations, primarily addressing space-related concepts, such as space contraction in SR and the light bending in GR. These mental representations manifested as mental imagery and mental simulations, aiding students in visualizing phenomena related to spatial concepts. This result is also consistent with the DCT, predicting that concrete phenomena, strongly linked to sensory experiences, tend to activate the nonverbal coding system.

It is crucial to observe that students who demonstrated an understanding of the theory exhibited evidence of these mental representations. Then, it appears that both coding systems, verbal and nonverbal, are essential for comprehending Relativity Theory. Therefore, in response to the research question proposed, it is observed that students used both verbal (propositional) and nonverbal (imagistic) mental representations to process the relativistic phenomena approached, primarily involving time and space.

These findings underscore the importance of comprehending and analysing the mental representations students develop in their learning processes of complex theories. This information becomes pivotal for devising effective teaching strategies that foster a deeper understanding of

the phenomena explained by these theories.

Furthermore, the analytical framework applied in this study can be extended to explore other themes within Modern and Contemporary Physics, as well as across various Science topics. Such an extension contributes to a better understanding of students' cognitive processes and facilitates the promotion of meaningful and high-quality education.

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